

MAIN GOALS OF PRODUCTION OF THE MAIN TYPES OF LIVESTOCK PRODUCTS IN THE REGIONS AND MECHANISMS FOR ITS IMPLEMENTATION

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Abstract: This thesis provides a comprehensive analysis of the main goals of livestock production and the mechanisms for their implementation based on economic and statistical methods. The current mechanisms for increasing the efficiency of livestock production in the regions are studied, and proposals and recommendations for their improvement are developed.

Keywords: main types of livestock products, milk, eggs, meat, agricultural sector, economic and statistical methods, mechanism.

In Uzbekistan, the livestock sector is one of the main directions of agriculture, and the efficient use of natural resources, labor, and land and water resources serves to ensure the stability of the domestic consumer market. Surkhandarya region is especially favorable for the development of livestock farming: its climate, pastures, fodder resources, and the availability of enterprises create the basis for the growth of the industry.

By region, cattle and sheep breeding are widely developed in Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya, and Jizzakh regions. Andijan, Namangan, and Fergana regions are mainly specialized in the production of dairy and poultry products. The Republic of Karakalpakstan and Bukhara regions stand out as regions with great potential in the field of cattle breeding and sheep breeding due to their pasture areas and natural resources.

The ongoing research shows that the livestock sector plays an important role not only in meeting the needs of the domestic market, but also in increasing export potential, creating new jobs, and improving the well-being of the population in rural areas. The year-on-year increase in Uzbekistan's livestock production indicators - especially in meat, milk, and eggs - demonstrates significant economic opportunities in this sector.

For example, when analyzing the state of livestock production in Uzbekistan in January-June 2025, 6.2% of meat production belonged to farms, 86.0% to dehqan and subsidiary farms, and 7.8% to organizations. By dairy products, this distribution is: farmers - 6.6%, dekhkans and household plot owners - 91.9%, and agricultural

organizations - 1.5%. In egg production, 16.4% were farmers, 55.0% were dehkans and household plot owners, and 28.6% were organizations.

Currently, the share of agriculture, in particular, the livestock sector, is significantly increasing in the economy of Uzbekistan. This sphere plays an important role not only in ensuring food security, but also in strengthening economic stability. Therefore, the need to increase the economic interest of livestock producers, stimulate their active participation in the market, and create a stable competitive environment in the industry is growing day by day.

For the effective organization of this process, it is necessary to introduce comprehensive mechanisms for the development and stimulation of livestock markets. In this regard, it is important, first of all, to create opportunities for producers to adapt to market requirements, to present their products at competitive prices, and to improve market infrastructure. It is also possible to effectively organize the activities of manufacturers by expanding their financial capabilities, providing them with modern technologies, and regularly familiarizing them with market information. It is also possible to effectively organize the activities of manufacturers by expanding their financial capabilities, providing them with modern technologies, and regularly familiarizing them with market information. At the same time, state support for producers, increasing their economic interest, and market mechanisms are being implemented.

Based on our research, we have developed mechanisms for stimulating the production of basic types of livestock products and livestock markets in the regions. This mechanism is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Mechanisms for stimulating livestock production and livestock markets in the regions¹

Figure 1 shows a comprehensive mechanism for stimulating the production of livestock products in the regions. This mechanism represents a systematic approach

¹ The drawing is based on the author's developments.

aimed at ensuring the effective development of the livestock industry. The complex mechanism shown in this figure represents a systematic approach to stimulating the production of livestock products in the regions. This mechanism includes such key elements as the effective use of local resources, the introduction of innovative technologies, support for manufacturers, and the development of local markets. Such an approach serves to ensure the sustainable development of the livestock industry.

World experience shows that the structural reorganization of agriculture is one of the most complex areas in the process of market reforms at the regional level. This is mainly due to the complex and multifaceted structure of the food system in the agricultural sector, as well as the specific political and geographical factors of the region.

To overcome this complexity, it is important to scientifically determine the priorities of structural policy. In particular, positive results can be achieved in ensuring food security through a self-regulating model of regional markets. Therefore, the integration of market mechanisms by the state with regulatory measures is important in the formation of long-term and sustainable structural transformations.

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